

Fateha Aziz
PhD candidate, University of Worcester
fateha.aziz@yahoo.com
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Reconfiguring Mankind: Metamodern Approaches in

Selected Terry Pratchett's Children's Titles

For Terry Pratchett, fantasy has a reconstructive purpose; that apart from “...talking animals and swords..., [it] also speculates about the future, rewrites the past and reconsiders the present.”¹ Inspired by that, this study will expand these acts into the notion of reconfiguring mankind from the metamodern viewpoint. I propose that the metamodern acts of oscillation and reconstruction, coupled with the reconstructive property of fantasy that Pratchett employs in the selected works effectively serve as a literary critique on the contemporary world.

Various settings and predicaments notwithstanding, the stories are however uniformed by the characters' realisation that many metanarratives such as conventional social systems and political constructs that make up their society have resulted in dire consequences. To solve conflicts, the characters take the existing systems, deconstruct and then reconstruct it into new solutions. To achieve reconstruction, they first oscillate between the existing ways and their doubt towards it, as well as between childhood and responsibilities that children do not normally undertake. However at the end of the stories, the characters all look forward to the future with a hopeful eye, but one that is aware of possible dire ramifications and thus in the metamodern spirit, become prepared to continuously deconstruct and reconstruct the world as they go. Via these methods, Pratchett is able to offer a commentary on the current social constructs while at the same time, empower the child characters and readers alike with cautious hope and possible mechanics to deal with today's world.

¹ Pratchett, Terry. “Let There Be Dragons.” *The L-Space Web*. n.d. Web. 25 April 2013.

Brief bio:

Fateha Aziz is currently doing a metamodern study on Terry Pratchett's children's fiction for her PhD at the University of Worcester. Her research interests include metamodernism in children's literature, fantasy, and ecocriticism, among others.